

LONG-TERM SEAWATER AGEING EFFECT ON FATIGUE CRACK GROWTH OF CFRP FOR MARINE PROPELLERS

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ABSTRACT

This paper describes the influence of long-term immersion in seawater on the crack propagation behaviour in composites. The composite studied is an epoxy resin reinforced by continuous carbon fibres. Crack propagation tests were performed under mode I and mode II static and cyclic loading. Seawater diffusion into the material was found to be Fickian and tests were carried out on specimens unaged, seawater saturated and dried after saturation. Saturated mode I and mode II specimens lose fracture resistance compared to dry specimens. However, after drying mode II fracture energy is recovered, while losses measured under mode I loading are permanent.

1 INTRODUCTION

Reducing pollution and greenhouse gases is a major objective in our modern society as our environmental impact has been clearly demonstrated. Developing new ways to produce energy is one of the solutions to reduce our environmental impact, another would be to reduce emissions produced by the currently developed technologies. In the maritime domain, marine renewable energies and marine transport are two subjects of interest where such improvements are possible.

Much recent research and development in marine renewable energies has focused on tidal, wave, and thermal energy converters. The principle of tidal turbines is to convert kinetic energy created by streams and tidal currents in the same way that wind turbines convert kinetic energy of the air created by winds. From a mechanical point of view, tidal turbines differ from wind turbines by their geometry. Whereas modern high-energy production wind turbines are over 150 meters in diameter, the dimensions of tidal turbine demonstrators are closer to 10-20 meters in diameter. As water is denser than air, dimensioning needs to take higher stress levels into account.

The use of composite materials to replace conventional metallic ship propellers also offers advantages that are expected to lower energy consumption [1-3]. The main advantage is an expected 50% propeller weight reduction. Other advantages would be improved engine efficiency by using the morphing ability of composites to obtain shape optimization at the operating speed.

From a mechanical point of view, tidal turbines and marine propellers are quite similar systems. Despite having different rotational speeds, they are both continuously immersed in seawater resulting in coupling of long-term seawater ageing and fatigue loading. Seawater ageing has been shown to influence mechanical properties for a large variety of composite materials [4]. However, there are few data on coupling of long-term seawater ageing and fatigue crack growth of composites [5]. Delamination behaviour of Fibre Reinforced Polymers (FRPs) has, for its part, been studied and normalized for different applications such as aircraft, wind turbines, and civil engineering [8-10].

Preliminary fatigue studies in four point bending – which corresponds to the expected main loading of the turbine blades and propellers – showed that the material was sensitive to seawater ageing and that the effect was partly reversible. As the predominant failure mode occurring during those tests was delamination, this led the study to concentrate on the sensitivity of crack growth properties to seawater ageing.

In this study, the aim was to evaluate the influence of seawater ageing on the fatigue crack growth properties of a carbon fibre reinforced epoxy for tidal turbine and marine propeller blade applications.

First, the material of study and the test methods will be described. Then results from the different fatigue tests will be shown and discussed. Finally, the effect of long-term seawater ageing on fatigue crack properties will be presented.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 MATERIAL STUDIED

The material of study is a carbon fibre reinforced epoxy. The reinforcement matrix prepolymers are diglycidylether of bisphenol F (DGEBF), diglycidylether of bisphenol A (DGEBA) and hexadeniol diglycidylether and the hardener is amine based. This commercial resin is made by Sicomin[®] and its glass transition temperature (T_g) has been measured by Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) to be 75 °C. The reinforcement fibres are unidirectional T700 from Torayca[®] with a tensile modulus of $E_f = 230$ GPa. The composite plates were produced by the infusion process, with a 6 plies unidirectional stacking sequence. A 13 μm thick by 80 mm wide Teflon film was placed at mid thickness at the two opposite sides of the composite plates to act as a starter crack. The fibre volume ratio was measured by thermo-gravimetric analysis to be $V_f = 55\%$.

2.2 METHODS

This study concentrates on the quasi-static and fatigue crack properties according to mode I and mode II loading (Fig. 1). The mode I tests were performed according to the ISO 15024 Double Cantilever Beam (DCB) standard test method. For mode II, there are several test methods but ISO 15114: Edge Loaded Split (ELS) geometry was chosen because of the larger crack length and crack stability compared to the other test methods.

Fig. 1: Visualization of the three different crack modes of composite

For each sample, a quasi-static pre-crack was made in order to cross the resin-rich zone in front of the insert. For the quasi-static tests, a crosshead speed of 1 mm/min was chosen and images of the side of the specimen were recorded at one frame per second. The specimen's side was painted white, to increase crack visibility (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2: Mode II ELS test apparatus

The fatigue tests were made at a 2Hz frequency using an electrical actuator. The tests were displacement controlled. Measurements of the crack opening displacement were made with an LVDT and loads were measured with a 500N load cell.

Data analysis was based on the Compliance Calibration (CC) calculation method because of good interpolation of the crack length during the fatigue tests. Calculation of the crack strain energy release rate used the Berry equation:

$$G_{Ic} = \frac{n \times P \times \delta}{2 \times b \times a} \quad (1)$$

In this equation, n is the compliance C vs crack length a so that $n = \frac{\partial \log(C)}{\partial \log(a)}$; P is the load, δ is the crack opening and b is the specimen width.

Seawater ageing was performed using constantly renewed seawater baths filled with natural seawater from Brest estuary. Kinetics of diffusion were experimentally measured by weighing 3 and 1 mm thick 50x50 mm² square composite samples.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 SEAWATER UPTAKE

Fig. 3: Water uptake of 1 and 3 mm thick composite samples in seawater at 60°C

Kinetics of diffusion were determined experimentally at four different temperatures: 4, 25, 40, and 60°C. A Fickian behaviour was identified by plotting the 1 and 3 mm weight uptakes as a function of the square root of time divided by the sample's thickness as shown for the 60°C condition in Fig. 2. One can see that 1 and 3mm thick samples show the same behaviour, with a first linear increase reaching a plateau for the 1 mm sample at around 1.2%. Mass at saturation was measured for the 60 and 40°C at 1.2% and has been considered to be the same for the 4 and 25°C conditions, even though it could differ from what is measured at the other temperatures. This allows calculation of the diffusion coefficients D and theoretical times to saturation for a 3 mm thick sample as listed in Table 1.

Ageing temperature	4°C	25°C	40°C	60°C
Time to saturation for 3mm thick composite (days)	2985	990	682	129
Diffusion coefficient ($\cdot 10^{-14} \text{m}^2/\text{s}$)	2,7	8,3	12	63

Table 1: Diffusion coefficients and theoretical times to saturation for seawater ageing of composite at different temperatures

The temperature dependence of the coefficient of diffusion can be evaluated using an Arrhenius plot, which gives, here, a good agreement to the Arrhenius law as shown in Fig. 3. The use of the activation energy (here measured at 40 kJ/mol) allows behavior at different temperatures to be estimated.

Fig. 4. Arrhenius plot of diffusion coefficient for the composite in seawater

As the thickness of the DCB and ELS samples is around 3 mm, the samples were saturated in seawater at 60°C for 4 months. The same time was used to dry the specimens after full saturation. The drying procedure was carried out in desiccators at 60°C.

3.2 EFFECT OF SEAWATER ON THE MODE I CRACK PROPERTIES

The aim of this part was to evaluate the ageing effect of seawater present in the composite on the mode I fatigue and quasi-static properties. To do so, a total of 30 samples was tested. Half of this total was used for quasi-static and half for the fatigue tests. A first batch of samples was tested as received. The latter will be referred to as the *Unaged* condition and it will represent the initial properties of the composite. The remaining samples were immersed in seawater at 60°C during 4 months so that the material was fully saturated. At this stage, a series of samples was tested. This batch aims to evaluate the influence of seawater ageing and will be referred to as *Saturated*. Finally, the remaining saturated samples were fully dried as explained in the previous section. Those samples will be referred to as *Saturated then dried*. This final condition will determine the reversibility of the ageing effect of seawater.

Fig. 5: Energy release rate in mode I

There is variability in the experimental response as shown in Fig. 5, which presents the quasi-static response of four *Saturated then dried* specimens. Then, for each ageing condition, one representative specimen has been chosen to illustrate the response. The crack response of the composite can then be compared as a function of the ageing condition (Fig. 6).

Fig. 6: Seawater effect on Mode I quasistatic delamination

It is possible to summarize the mechanical response by comparing the curves highest points. Those points correspond to the energy released when the crack advances. Thus, the average energy release rate starts at a value of $G_{I,initial} = 840 \pm 90 \text{ J/m}^2$ and drops to $G_{I,Saturated} = 625 \pm 109 \text{ J/m}^2$ after full saturation. This drop represents a decrease of around 25% of the initial value. After being fully dried, the energy release rate decreases again to an average value of $G_{I,Dried} = 578 \pm 57 \text{ J/m}^2$, which represents a decrease of 30% from the initial energy. This result shows that the effect of seawater ageing is not reversible otherwise the dried energy release rate would be close to the initial unaged value. These results are contradictory to some published values [9-12]. The behaviour found in those articles shows an increase of the energy release rate after saturation of the material. This increase was justified by plasticization thanks to the increased resin's ductility. Here, plasticization of the resin was not set aside but the presence of another ageing phenomenon was considered. In fact mechanical tests performed on the pure resin showed the presence of both plasticization and physical ageing during

ageing characterization. Physical ageing has an opposite effect on the resin's mechanical behaviour as it reduces the ductility while increasing maximal stress. Plasticization is reversible on drying the material while physical ageing is not sensitive to water content but to thermal exposure which could justify the non-reversible behaviour seen here.

Fig. 7: Seawater effect on Mode I fatigue crack properties

The same observation can be made on the fatigue properties as showed in Fig. 7. One can identify a semi-reversible ageing effect, as the dried condition tend to partially recover the initial fatigue behavior. It worth noting that the ageing effect is more important when considering the high crack growth rates and less important for the low delamination rates.

The ageing behavior differ between quasi-static and cyclic loading. This behavior is not clearly understood and further tests on the effect of physical ageing could explain this change in behavior.

3.3 EFFECT OF SEAWATER ON THE MODE II CRACK PROPERTIES

Fig. 8: Seawater effect on Mode II quasi-static delamination

Mode II delamination was characterized using the same procedure as for mode I in the previous section of this article. Mode II showed higher variability during quasi-static tests. The value of released energy at crack advance have been measured and summarized in Fig. 8.

In this case, seawater ageing shows a semi-reversible effect on the delamination energy. The presence of seawater decreases the energy release rate from $G_{II,Initial} \approx 1690 \pm 300 \text{ J/m}^2$ to $G_{II,Saturated} \approx 1260 \pm 280 \text{ J/m}^2$, which represents a decrease of 25 % comparable to what was measured in Mode I previously. The main difference is when considering the fully saturated then dried condition; under in-plane shear, drying tends to partly recover the initial energy release rate with an average value of $G_{I,Dried} = 1510 \pm 200 \text{ J/m}^2$, which is 10% less than the initial value.

Fig. 9: Seawater effect on Mode II fatigue crack properties

Fatigue tests once again showed reversibility of the seawater ageing effect with the difference that the dried behavior is recovered or even slightly higher than that of the initial state. The effect of seawater induces a quasi-constant drop of the fatigue behavior (Fig. 9). For the same crack growth rate level, the necessary energy release rate is on average 100 J/m^2 less for the saturated specimens compared to the initial and dried conditions.

This result is in accordance with published values [5, 11, 12]. Mode I and Mode II load the resin and the interface to different extents, which could explain the difference in behavior when comparing the results from those two modes.

4 CONCLUSION

This article shows the sensitivity of a carbon fibre reinforced epoxy to seawater ageing. First, the diffusion kinetics were characterized for different temperatures. A Fickian behaviour was identified and the composite's mass gain at saturation was measured to be 1.2%.

The mode I and mode II crack propagation properties of the composite were determined according to three different ageing conditions: unaged, fully saturated in seawater, and saturated in seawater then fully dried. The measured mode I and mode II energy release rate showed a decrease of 25% under quasi-static loading. This decrease was not reversible in mode I but partly reversible in mode II.

When considering fatigue loading, seawater ageing induces a loss of the strain energy release rate at an equivalent crack growth rate for both mode I and mode II. The ageing effect is more important for higher crack growth rates in mode I while it is more or less constant in mode II. The reversibility is more important for the mode II tests, as the fatigue curve recovers its initial form. For mode I, the behaviour was only partly recovered.

A combination of plasticization and physical ageing contribute to the different behaviours shown in this article. Further experimental tests being performed on the pure resin should lead to a better understanding of the mechanisms involved in interlaminar fracture under conditions representative of marine turbine blade and propeller applications.

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